

Development of a Data Management Resource to Support Animal-Free Toxicity Testing and Human Risk Assessment

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ASPIS

Abstract

A requirement of the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation funding program is that the three funded consortia; ONTOX, PrecisionTox, and RISK-HUNT3R; collaborate on cross-consortia projects. This collaborative group, ASPIS (Animal-free Safety Assessment of Chemicals: Project Cluster for Implementation of Novel Strategies), consist of over 70 institutions across 16 European countries and the United States. It utilizes available and newly generated data to improve the accuracy, speed, and affordability of chemical risk assessment without the use of laboratory animals. The goals of the three consortia overlap but are distinct. ONTOX uses a generic strategy to predict systemic repeated dose toxicity effects in combination with exposure assessment. PrecisionTox applies multi-omics, computational approaches, and genetic variation to understand fundamental mechanisms of chemicals toxicity, while reducing traditional animal testing assessment. RISK-HUNT3R is developing, validating, and implementing integrated approaches to assess chemical exposure, toxicokinetics, and toxicodynamics for the development of next-generation risk assessment strategies. To support the efforts of ASPIS, a common database is being developed that will include cheminformatics, in vivo and in vitro toxicity data, transcriptomic and metabolomic data from multiple species, policy, legal and risk assessment documents, mathematical and theoretical models, and novel tools to analyze this information. The ASPIS-wide database will contain diverse and evolving information not typically found in a single database and support users with varied questions. The creation of this database requires coordinating the input from multiple end-users with diverse needs, requirements and project goals and database developers with varied skill sets. Additionally, efforts and timelines of database development teams within each consortium must be accommodated. A project coordinator has been assigned to facilitate the development of the ASPIS-wide data management resource. Organizational schemes, challenges, opportunities, and successes will be presented.